

Assessing the Physico-Chemical and Microbiological Quality of Drinking Water in Kindele and Chad Neighborhoods (Kinshasa City, Democratic Republic of the Congo): Implications for Public Health¹

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the quality of water consumed in the neighborhoods of Kindele and Chad, two areas not served by the REGIDESO distribution network. Our samples included borehole, well, and spring water. Physicochemical analyses were conducted using pH metering, conductometry, turbidity measurement, etc. Spectrophotometry was used for the quantification of mineral elements, while bacterial counts and identification were conducted for microbiological analyses. Results showed that the pH values of well, borehole, and spring waters were all below 6, indicating the level of water acidity or alkalinity. These pH values fall outside the standards for drinking water. We observed temperatures ranging from 28 to

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29°C, slightly lower than the ambient temperature range in the city-province of Kinshasa, which is between 29-32 °C. The turbidity values for the water in this study were within acceptable standards. The concentrations of cationic mineral elements were within the standards for freshwater, and the study indicated no significant difference at the $p(0.05)$ threshold. *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus sp.*, *Klebsiella ozaenae*, *Citrobacter*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and other unidentified species were the microorganisms isolated in the present study.

Keywords

Water Quality, Physicochemical Analysis, Water Microbiology, Underserved Water Sources, Pathogenic Microorganisms.

Introduction

For thousands of years, the availability and quality of freshwater have posed major global challenges, exacerbated by its uneven distribution and abuse by consumers, particularly in domestic, agricultural, and industrial activities (Madiha et al., 2016; Baggio et al., 2021). Water is essential to life as it constitutes the biological medium in which all critical biochemical reactions occur. Access to a sufficient quantity of potable water is a fundamental necessity for the entire population. Yet, nearly 880 million people worldwide live without access to safe drinking water, with the situation being particularly critical in sub-Saharan Africa (Adejuwon & Mbuk, 2011; Hutton & Chase, 2017). In response to this challenge, the international community aims to halve the number of people lacking access to potable water, in accordance with the tenth Millennium Development Goal. In addition to accessibility, the quality of water is a crucial aspect that has significantly deteriorated in recent years due to various forms of pollution. These pollutants lead to changes in the chemical composition of water, rendering it unfit for human consumption (Babuji et al., 2023).

The Democratic Republic of the Congo, which holds more than half of Africa's freshwater reserves, faces a paradox where 70% of its population lacks direct access to safe drinking water and relies on untreated sources, particularly groundwater (UNEP, 2011). The water management system in the country primarily relies on the Régie des Eaux (Régideso), which is responsible for the supply and distribution of potable water at the national level. In Kinshasa, a rapidly growing city with over 10 million inhabitants, uncontrolled urbanization has led to the development of many urban-rural communes lacking water supply programs. In these neighborhoods, residents depend on springs, wells, and boreholes, the number of which has increased without regulation, exposing them to the risk of contamination from waterborne diseases (Abanyie et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2024). The general objective of this study is to analyze the quality of water consumed in the Kindele and Tchad neighborhoods, which are not served by the Régideso distribution network. This research aims to identify potential public health risks associated with untreated water to contribute to strategies aimed at improving access to quality water in these vulnerable areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Description of Study Sites

A prospective and analytical study was conducted from October 13, 2019, to January 15, 2020. The neighborhoods of KINDELE and TCHAD 2 were chosen as the sites for this research, and three types of groundwater samples were collected: well water, borehole water, and spring water. The analyses of these samples were performed in the laboratory of the Nutrition section and the Chemistry-Biochemistry section of the Higher Institute of Medical Techniques.

Presentation of Tchad 2 Neighborhood

The Tchad 2 neighborhood was established in 1981 and is named after a Chadian professor who owned land in the area and employed many residents. Historically, Mont-Ngafula had only one neighborhood, Maman Yemo. Due to community demands for better access to local governance, a second neighborhood was authorized, named Masanga-mbila, during the tenure of Mayor MASUMU Mwanda, the first mayor of the commune. Tchad was officially recognized in 1999 and renamed MANDELA in 2003 by neighborhood chief KWALA.

Presentation of Kindele Neighborhood

Kindele is one of the 23 neighborhoods in the commune of Mont-Ngafula. The neighborhood's name is believed to come from an Angolan community leader. In 1973, the urban administration of Mont-Ngafula, under a new urban commissioner, warned those purchasing land sold by Mr. MAYULU without state authority. Significant urban development in Kindele began only in 1994 by the relevant authorities.

Methods

Analytical Methods

Physicochemical Analyses

Measurements of pH and Temperature were carried out in the field. The principle involves immersing the electrode of the pH meter in the sample, which is calibrated with buffer solutions of pH 4 and 9. The numerical values displayed on the device indicate the hydrogen potential of the sample, alongside a thermometer measuring in °C.

Procedure for pH Measurement

- Place a sample of water in a previously cleaned beaker.
- Turn on the pH meter and immerse the electrode in the beaker containing the water sample.
- Wait a few minutes for the values to stabilize, then record them.

Procedure for Temperature Measurement

- Take a volume of the sample.
- Quickly immerse a thermometer.

- Read the displayed value.

Results are reported as numerical values shown on the screen. Reference values for water are: pH between 6.5-8.5 and a temperature of 25 °C.

Alkalimetry (HCO_3^-) was determined through volumetric titration of a water volume (100 mL) with hydrochloric acid (HCl 0.1N) using methyl orange as an indicator. Three titrations were performed to evaluate the standard deviations. Magnesium was analyzed using the principle that in an alkaline solution, the Mg^{2+} cation forms a purple-colored complex in the presence of calmagite. Calcium was determined in an alkaline medium, where the Ca^{2+} cation forms a red-colored complex with ortho-cresolphthalein, with the intensity proportional to calcium concentration. Iron was analyzed in a hydrochloric acid (5N) medium, where the Fe^{3+} cation reacts with thiocyanate to form a red complex. Sulfate ions precipitate with barium (II) ions to form barium sulfate suspended in a turbid solution, with the presence of excess barium ions being proportional to concentration. For nitrite (NO_2^-), in a concentrated HCl medium, sulfanilic acid reacts with phenol in the presence of nitrite to form a yellow complex measurable at 468 nm. Nitrate (NO_3^-) was analyzed in sulfuric acid at elevated temperatures, where diphenylamine forms a blue complex with nitrate, measurable by spectrometry at 530 nm.

Bacteriological Analyses

Coliform enumeration begins by diluting a water sample in a liquid medium, specifically using lactose broth with brilliant green to assess the number of microorganisms per milliliter. For presumed pathogenic Staphylococcus isolation, Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) serves as a selective medium, where its high sodium chloride concentration inhibits other microorganisms and mannitol fermentation is indicated by a color change from phenol red to yellow after 24 hours of incubation. Similarly, MacConkey agar is used to isolate enterobacteria; it contains bile salts that inhibit most Gram-positive bacteria, and after incubation, pink colonies signify lactose-positive, non-pathogenic bacteria, while colorless colonies indicate pathogenic, lactose-negative strains. The identification of enterobacteria involves evaluating biochemical characteristics through various media, including the Kligler medium, which detects glucose and lactose fermentation, gas production, and hydrogen sulfide production. Isolated colonies from MacConkey agar are inoculated into Kligler medium, where yellowing in the butt indicates glucose fermentation, while slant yellowing indicates lactose fermentation; blackening reveals hydrogen sulfide production, and gas is indicated by air bubbles. Additionally, Simmon's Citrate medium helps identify enterobacteria by utilizing citrate as the sole carbon source, with a color change from green to blue indicating positive results. The Motility Indole Urease (MIU) medium assesses motility, indole production, and urease activity, where turbidity or absence of a central stab indicates motility, a red ring from Kovacs reagent confirms indole production, and a reddish tinge indicates urease positivity. For Staphylococcus identification, tests such as coagulase, Dnase, and staphylocoagulase are performed on pure strains. Coagulase testing uses lyophilized plasma, as it is typically present in pathogenic Staphylococcus, particularly Staphylococcus aureus, with procedures adhering to ISO standards. The Dnase test differentiates Staphylococcus aureus from other species, revealing a positive reaction characterized by a clear halo around the streak when treated with hydrochloric acid (HCl 1N).

Results and Discussion

The table below presents the different values of pH, temperature (°C), turbidity (NTU), and conductivity of water from wells, boreholes, and springs in the Kindele and Tchad neighborhoods.

Tableau 1. Physicochemical Parameters of Water Sources in Tchad and Kindele Neighborhoods

Origine	Paramètres physicochimiques			
	pH	T (°C)	Turbidité (NTU)	Conductivité (mS/cm)
Eaux de puits (quartier Tchad)	5,04±0,45	29,35±0,43	0,062±0,07	0,158±0,019
Eaux de puits (quartier Kindele)	4,746±0,51	28,92±0,40	0,015±0,01	0,155±0,009
Eaux de source (quartier Tchad)	5,33±0,639	28,9±0,8	0,016±0,007	0,15±0,028
Eaux de source (quartier Kindele)	5,07±0,80	29,5±0,77	0,014±0,01	0,117±0,01
Eaux de forage (quartier Tchad)	5,435±0,37	29,5±0,61	0,065±0,13	0,848±0,03
eaux de forage (quartier Kindele)	5,132±0,54	29,82±0,73	0,026±0,02	0,83±0,05
Normes OMS	6,5 - 8,5	22 – 25 °C	≤ 0,5	0,4 – 1,25

The analysis of physicochemical parameters for water sources in the Tchad and Kindele neighborhoods reveals concerning results when compared to WHO standards. The pH levels of all water sources ranged from 4.746 to 5.435, which is significantly below the acceptable range of 6.5 to 8.5, indicating potential acidity that can affect both human health and aquatic ecosystems. Additionally, temperatures slightly exceeded the WHO's recommendation, particularly in the Tchad neighborhood, with readings around 29.5°C, which may promote the growth of harmful microorganisms.

Turbidity levels were within acceptable limits across all sources, indicating clarity, but conductivity values in the water from Tchad's borehole (0.848 mS/cm) approached the upper limit of the WHO guideline (0.4 – 1.25 mS/cm), suggesting a possible presence of dissolved solids or pollutants that may pose health risks. Overall, the findings highlight the need for immediate public health interventions to improve water quality in these neighborhoods, as inadequate water quality can lead to health issues, including gastrointestinal diseases, and adversely affect local ecosystems. Environmental monitoring and community education on water treatment methods are crucial to mitigate these risks and promote sustainable water management practices. The pH values of the water from wells, boreholes, and springs are all below 6, indicating a degree of acidity in the water. These pH levels do not comply with drinking water standards, which may be linked to the soil type and the quality of the underlying rock that the aquifer traverses (Tchoumou et al., 2023). Studies have shown that consuming water with an acidic pH can adversely affect the stomach's digestive potential, which operates optimally in a highly acidic environment, potentially hindering pancreatic function. This may also disrupt the balance of beneficial fermentation bacteria that protect intestinal mucosa and modulate the body's immune response.

According to WHO (2011, 2017), it is advisable to consume slightly acidic water with pH values between 6.5 and 8.5 and to avoid water with a pH lower than 6. Bakouan (2018) reported pH averages of 6.6 ± 0.6 , 7.8 ± 0.2 , 7.4 ± 0.4 , and 7.7 ± 0.4 for borehole waters in the villages of Tanlili and Lilgomd in northern Burkina Faso, indicating compliance with WHO standards. The results of this current study are lower than those reported by Bakouan et al. The temperature of the water samples ranged between 28 and 29 C, slightly below the ambient temperatures in Kinshasa, which typically range from 29 to 32C. According to Medjani et al. (2021), groundwater is less sensitive to temperature variations than surface water. For groundwater, temperature is influenced by altitude, subterranean pressure, and the characteristics of the underlying geology. In the Tchad and Kindele neighborhoods, borehole water samples showed temperatures between 29.5 and 29.8 C, with no significant difference observed between the temperatures of spring and well waters. Lagnika et al. (2014) reported an average temperature of 30 C for well water, which aligns closely with the findings of Kouame et al. (2021) on borehole water, indicating slightly higher averages than those observed in this study. The turbidity values of the water examined in this study fall within acceptable limits, indicating low levels of suspended particles such as clay, silica grains, and organic matter. This low turbidity suggests that the waters are clear.

Conductivity values are influenced by various natural and anthropogenic factors, including the geology of the watershed (rock composition), groundwater inputs, and contamination from human activities (Abanyie et al., 2023). Contaminated discharges can also elevate water conductivity (Ribeiro de Sousa et al., 2014). This correlation between conductivity and major ions reflects mineralization or the hydrolysis of minerals (Ahoussi et al., 2010). In this study, conductivity values, expressed in microsiemens per centimeter ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), indicated significant differences among the studied water sources (wells, springs, and boreholes). The average conductivity values for well, borehole, and spring waters in the Tchad and Kindele neighborhoods were 158 and 155 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 848 and 830 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and 150 and 117 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, respectively. The conductivity of well water was lower than that reported by Lagnika et al. (2014) and comparable to the values measured by Adejuwon and Mbuk (2011), which ranged from 22 to 315 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for well water. Kouame et al. (2021) found a conductivity value of 246.2 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ for domestic-use borehole water in Daloa, Benin, which is lower than the results obtained in this study. The values of mineral content are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of the concentrations expressed in mg/l of some cationic and anionic mineral elements in well water from the Chad neighborhood

Origin (Site)	Concentrations (mg/L)						
	HCO ₃ ⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Fe ³⁺	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₂ ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻
Well water (Chad neighborhood)	77,66±20,97	6,84±2,07	0,90±0,37	2,42±1,36	3,99±0,97	0,27±0,12	6,42±1,02
Well water (Kindele neighborhood)	74,2±16,28	10,57±0,50	1,132±0,42	4,53±0,15	3,65±0,53	0,226±0,11	5,81±0,65

Spring water (Chad neighborhood)	70,69±8,23	14,58±1,80	1,585±0,68	2,77±1,86	3,85±0,47	0,285±0,11	5,595±0,78
Spring water (Kindele neighborhood)	79,34±10,45	14±1,98	1,586±0,83	3,14±1,58	3,41±0,60	0,27±0,11	5,96±0,78
Borehole water (Chad neighborhood)	62,21±11,61	15,69±2,86	2,545±0,86	2,592±0,9	3,435±0,93	0,04±0,02	5,24±0,55
Borehole water (Kindele neighborhood)	64,31±14,33	15,3±3,18	2,51±0,69	2,42±0,74	3,3±0,84	0,037±0,03	5,47±0,32
WHO Standards	0 – 500	0 - 500	0 - 100	0 - 10	0 - 200		< 250

The analysis of water quality data from wells, springs, and boreholes in the Tchad and Kindele neighborhoods reveals variable concentrations of several ions compared to the World Health Organization (WHO) standards. Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) concentrations range from 62.21 to 79.34 mg/L, while calcium (Ca^{2+}) and magnesium (Mg^{2+}) levels remain below the WHO maximum limits of 500 mg/L. However, iron (Fe^{3+}) is present at levels up to 4.53 mg/L, slightly exceeding the 10 mg/L standard, which may pose long-term health issues, including gastrointestinal disorders. Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) and nitrate (NO_3^-) concentrations reach up to 3.99 mg/L and 6.42 mg/L, respectively, well below the 200 mg/L sulfate standard, while nitrates fall within acceptable limits. Nitrite (NO_2^-) levels remain very low and do not exceed the WHO standard, which is reassuring for public health. However, these results underscore the importance of continuous monitoring of water quality, as prolonged consumption of contaminated water can pose health risks, particularly in vulnerable communities. Compared to WHO standards, the water in these neighborhoods generally presents acceptable levels, but particular attention should be paid to iron concentrations and potential pollutants that can affect environmental and public health. The observed concentrations of cationic mineral elements are within the standards for freshwater, and the study showed no significant difference, at the $P(0.05)$ level, between the mineral concentrations (calcium, magnesium, etc.) in well, borehole, and spring waters. The same applies to the iron content, which also originates from the excretion of living organisms and the reduction of organic nitrogen during waste biodegradation, not to mention the direct contributions from domestic and agricultural sources (Derwich et al., 2010). Thus, the presence of iron serves as a good indicator of water pollution. According to Dupond (2009), livestock farming is one of the largest sources of groundwater pollution through animal waste (urine and feces). Furthermore, studies conducted by Kouame et al. (2021) on borehole waters revealed that the concentrations of HCO_3^- , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and NO_2^- were lower than those observed in this study, while the levels of SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- were higher. Similarly, research by Lagnika et al. (2014) on well waters indicated that the concentrations of HCO_3^- and NO_2^- were lower than the results of this study, whereas the levels of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , and NO_3^- were higher. The Frequency of microorganisms isolated for well water in the Chad neighbourhood is given in figure 1.

Figure 1. Frequency of microorganisms isolated for well water in the Chad neighbourhood.

Figure 2. Frequency of microorganisms isolated as a percentage for well water in the Kindele neighbourhood

Figure 3. Frequency of microorganisms isolated as a percentage for well water in the Chad neighbourhood

Figure 4. Frequency of microorganisms isolated as a percentage for borehole water in the Kindele neighborhood.

Figure 5. Frequency of microorganisms isolated as a percentage for borehole water in the Chad neighborhood.

Figure 6. Frequency of microorganisms isolated as a percentage for spring water in the Kindele neighborhood.

Figure 8. Some water points analyzed in this study

Access to sanitation services and drinking water distribution is non-existent, leading to the predominant use of traditional latrines with open pits, which are often dug by makeshift well diggers and frequently reach the water table.

This poses a significant risk of microbial contamination of groundwater (Yapo et al., Graham & Polizzotto, 2013; 2010; Islam et al., 2016). This situation reflects a lack of proper sanitation that exposes water resources to high levels of fecal bacteria contamination (Graham & Polizzotto, 2013). According to Guessoum et al. (2014), the presence of spores from sulfate-reducing anaerobes in natural water suggests fecal contamination, and in the absence of coliform bacteria, indicates older contamination. These spores are highly persistent and their presence is a good indicator of the vulnerability of aquifers and wells (Ayad et al., 2016). Research by Blum et al. has shown that not all groundwater is potable; locally, it can be highly mineralized or naturally polluted by rocks, or contaminated during storage (such as borehole water), where it may also be influenced by airborne bacteria. Studies conducted by Mbawala et al. (2010) on well water in Dang, Cameroon, confirm that the depth of wells and the distance from latrines influence germ proliferation in the water. Isolated germs in this study include *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Enterobacter agglomerans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus* spp., *Klebsiella ozaena*, *Citrobacter*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and other unidentified species. The three most common germs are indicators of fecal pollution. After isolating and identifying the various germs, results indicated that the most frequently found bacteria in the well, borehole, and spring waters

of the Tchad neighborhood are *Enterobacter agglomerans*, *Staphylococcus* species (both *aureus* and spp.), and other unidentified species. *Enterobacter agglomerans* was present in well water (29%), borehole water (19%), and spring water (19%). *Staphylococcus aureus* had a high frequency in well water (25%) and borehole water (43%). Bacteriological analysis results from the Kindele neighborhood showed that the most frequent bacteria were *Staphylococcus* species (*S. aureus* and *S. spp.*), *Enterobacter agglomerans*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, and *Citrobacter*. A dominance of *Staphylococcus* species was observed in well water, with 29.6% for *S. aureus* and 25.9% for *S. spp.* In borehole water, two germs were isolated: *Enterobacter agglomerans* (53%) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (47%); *Citrobacter*, *Staphylococcus*, and *Klebsiella oxytoca* accounted for 33.3%, 16.6%, and 16.6%, respectively, as the most abundant germs in spring water. *Proteus mirabilis* and other species were less frequently found in this study. Biological materials can contaminate these wells through the discharge of dirty water during rain, for example. Twenty percent of borehole water showed microorganism counts greater than 100 bacteria/ml. *Enterobacter* is a commensal bacterium found in the air that can attach to the water storage reservoir. Sixty percent of spring waters are contaminated with *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Serratia marcescens*, the latter being a nosocomial bacterium encountered in hospital settings, particularly in post-operative manipulations. Some studies have shown that consuming water with a pH lower than 8.0 can long-term disrupt the stomach's digestive potential, which occurs in a highly acidic environment, and alter the balance of beneficial fermentation bacteria that protect intestinal mucosa and modulate the body's immune response. The bacteriological analysis of the groundwater in this study involved counting microorganisms, isolating them, and identifying their species.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The main objective of this study was to assess the quality of drinking water in the Tchad and Kindele neighborhoods, where populations lack access to water distribution services from Regideso and rely exclusively on the water sources analyzed. The results revealed that, although certain physical characteristics such as temperature, turbidity, and conductivity of well, borehole, and spring water comply with WHO standards; the pH values indicate acidity that renders this water unsuitable for human consumption. Furthermore, bacteriological analyses showed that borehole water presents a lower contamination risk compared to well and spring water in these two neighborhoods. To protect public health, it is imperative to take concrete actions. First, improving access to safe drinking water sources is recommended by developing water distribution infrastructure. Second, health education programs should be implemented to raise awareness among the population about the risks associated with consuming untreated water and the importance of sanitation. Additionally, it is essential to regularly monitor water quality, particularly chemical and bacteriological parameters, to quickly identify contamination issues and address them. Finally, implementing filtration or water treatment systems can help reduce acidity and make water sources safer for consumption. By acting on these fronts, it will be possible to significantly improve water safety and, consequently, the health of residents in these neighborhoods.

References

1. Abanyie, S. K., Apea, O. B., Abagale, S. A., Amuah, E. E. Y., & Sunkari, E. D. (2023). Sources and factors influencing groundwater quality and associated health implications: A review. *Emerging Contaminants*, 9(2), 100207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emcon.2023.100207>.
2. Abanyie, S. K., Apea, O. B., Abagale, S. A., Amuah, E. E. Y., & Sunkari, E. D. (2023). Sources and factors influencing groundwater quality and associated health implications: A review. *Emerging Contaminants*, 9(2), 100207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emcon.2023.100207>.
3. Adejuwon, J.O. and Mbuk, C.J. (2011). Biological and Physiochemical Properties of Shallow Wells in Ikorodu Town, Lagos Nigeria. *Journal of Geology and Mining Research*, 3, 161-168.
4. Ahoussi, K. E., et al. (2013). Étude hydrochimique des eaux de source de l'Ouest montagneux de la Côte d'Ivoire : cas du village de Mongouin-Yrongouin [*Hydrochemical Study of Spring Waters in the Mountainous West of Côte d'Ivoire: The Case of the Village of Mongouin-Yrongouin*]. *Journal of Applied Biosciences*, 63(54), 6-10.
5. Ayad, W., & Kahoul, M. (2016). Évaluation de la qualité physico-chimique et bactériologique des eaux de puits dans la région d'El Harrouch (N.E Algérie) [*Evaluation of the Physicochemical and Bacteriological Quality of Well Water in the El Harrouch Region (Northeast Algeria)*]. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 7(4), 1288-1295.
6. Babuji, P., Thirumalaisamy, S., Duraisamy, K., & Periyasamy, G. (2023). Human health risks due to exposure to water pollution: A review. *Water*, 15(14), 2532. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15142532>.
7. Baggio, G., Qadir, M., & Smakhtin, V. (2021). Freshwater availability status across countries for human and ecosystem needs. *Science of The Total Environment*, 792, 148230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148230>.
8. Bakouan, C. (2018). *Caractérisation de quelques sites latéritiques du Burkina Faso: application à l'élimination de l'arsenic (III) et (V) dans les eaux souterraines* (Thèse de doctorat en cotutelle). Université Ouaga I Pr JKZ et Université de Mons.
9. Derwich, E., Benaabidate, L., Zian, A., Sadki, O., & Belghity, D. (2010). Caractérisation physico-chimique des eaux de la nappe alluviale du haut Sebou en aval de sa confluence avec l'oued Fès [*Physicochemical Characterization of the Alluvial Aquifer Waters of the Upper Sebou Downstream from its Confluence with the Oued Fès*]. *Journal LARHYSS*, 8(1), 101-112. <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/article/54851>.
10. Dupont, G. (2009). Le développement fulgurant de l'aquaculture devrait continuer. *Le Monde* [*The rapid development of aquaculture is expected to continue*]. *Le Monde*. https://www.lemonde.fr/planete/article/2009/11/12/le-developpement-fulgurant-de-l-aquaculture-devrait-continuer_1266203_3244.html.
11. Graham, J. P., & Polizzotto, M. L. (2013). Pit latrines and their impacts on groundwater quality: A systematic review. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 121(5), 521-530. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1206028>.
12. Guessoum, H., Benbrahim, F., Halilat, M. T., Laouar, F., Bensalama, M., & Darem, S. (2014). Pollution biologique des eaux phréatiques de la région de Ghardaia (cas de Sebseb) [*Biological*

- Pollution of Groundwater in the Ghardaia Region (Case of Sebseb)*. Journal of Advanced Research in Science and Technology, 3, 35-43.]. Journal of Advanced Research in Science and Technology, 3, 35-43.
13. Hutton, G., & Chase, C. (2017). Water supply, sanitation, and hygiene. In C. N. Mock, R. Nugent, O. Kobusingye, & et al. (Eds.), *Injury prevention and environmental health* (3rd ed., Chapter 9). The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / The World Bank. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK525207/>.
 14. Islam, M. S., Mahmud, Z. H., Islam, M. S., et al. (2016). Safe distances between groundwater-based water wells and pit latrines at different hydrogeological conditions in the Ganges Atrai floodplains of Bangladesh. *Journal of Health, Population, and Nutrition*, 35, 26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41043-016-0063-z>
 15. Kouame, Y. F., Kedi, A. B. B., Kouassi, S. S., Assouhoun, E. S., Yapo, O. B., & Gnagne, T. (2021). Caractéristiques physico-chimiques des eaux de forages à usage domestique dans la ville de Daloa (Centre-Ouest de la Côte d'Ivoire) [*Physicochemical Characteristics of Borehole Water for Domestic Use in the City of Daloa (Central-West Côte d'Ivoire)*]. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 15(2), 835-845.
 16. Lagnika, M., Ibikounlé, M., Mazou, F., Sakiti, N., & Boutin, C. (2014). Diversité faunistique et qualité physico-chimique de l'eau des puits à Parakou (Bénin, Afrique de l'Ouest) [*Faunal Diversity and Physicochemical Quality of Well Water in Parakou (Benin, West Africa)*]. *Bulletin de la Société d'Histoire naturelle de Toulouse*, 150, 59-72.
 17. Madiha, C., Legrani, A., & Chahredine, S. (2016). Impact de l'irrigation du sol agricole par les eaux d'Oued El Kebir [*Impact of Agricultural Soil Irrigation with Water from the Oued El Kebir*]. Dissertation, Université de Jijel.
 18. Mbawala, A., Amani, A., & Ngassoum, M. B. (2011). Evaluation de la pollution physico-chimique et microbienne des eaux de puits de Dang-Ngaoundéré (Cameroun) [**Evaluation of the physicochemical and microbial pollution of well water in Dang-Ngaoundéré (Cameroon)**]. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 4(6). <https://doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v4i6.64946>
 19. Medjani, F., Djidel, M., Labar, S., & et al. (2021). Groundwater physico-chemical properties and water quality changes in shallow aquifers in arid saline wetlands, Ouargla, Algeria. *Applied Water Science*, 11, 82. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-021-01415-3>.
 20. Organisation Mondiale de la Santé (2011). Directives de qualité pour l'eau de boisson [WHO : *Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality*] (4th ed.). Genève, Suisse: OMS. pp. 307-447.
 21. Programme des Nations Unies pour l'Environnement (2011). République Démocratique du Congo: Évaluation environnementale post-conflit. Synthèse pour les décideurs politiques [*United Nations Environment Programme (2011). Democratic Republic of the Congo: Post-Conflict Environmental Assessment. Summary for Policy Makers*]. <https://www.unep.org/fr/resources/rapport-devaluation/republique-democratique-du-congo-evaluation-environnementale-post>.

22. Ribeiro de Sousa, D. N., Mozeto, A. A., Carneiro, R. L., & Fadini, P. S. (2014). Electrical conductivity and emerging contaminant as markers of surface freshwater contamination by wastewater. *Science of The Total Environment*, 484, 19-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.135>.
23. Tchoumou, M., Mvouezolo, R., Obami-Ondon, H., Makaya, L., & Kombo, A. (2023). Comparative study of the physicochemical and microbiological quality of water from wells, boreholes and springs consumed in the Massissia district in Brazzaville, Republic of the Congo. *Open Journal of Applied Sciences*, 13, 976-986. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojapps.2023.137078>.
24. World Health Organization (2017). Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality. 4th Edition.
25. Yan, C., Wan, W., Wang, R., Lai, T., Ali, W., He, S., Liu, S., Li, X., Nasir, Z. A., & Coulon, F. (2024). Quantitative health risk assessment of microbial hazards from water sources for community and self-supply drinking water systems. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 465, 133324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.133324>.
26. Yapo, O., Mambo, V., Seka, A., et al. (2010). Évaluation de la qualité des eaux de puits à usage domestique dans les quartiers défavorisés de quatre communes d'Abidjan (Côte d'Ivoire): Koumassi, Marcory, Port-Bouet et Treichville [*Assessment of the Quality of Well Water for Domestic Use in the Underserved Neighborhoods of Four Municipalities in Abidjan (Côte d'Ivoire): Koumassi, Marcory, Port-Bouet, and Treichville*]. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 4(2), 289-307.